

**LEVELS OF UNDERSTANDING OF THE ARTWORK
AND THEIR POSSIBLE CONTRADICTIONARY CLASH**

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Abstract: This article discusses the difficulties of understanding a literary text, since the understanding of a literary text moves from verbal to substantive, the combination of which gives a logical understanding; from it, the movement is directed to understanding motives, goals, and subtext. In this direction, approximately, the process of perception of the actual and emotional-artistic content of the work takes place.

Key words and phrases: emotional-artistic, complex, contradictory process, clarification, perception, imagination, right combination, personality.

There are two levels in the content of a work of art: one of them is the actual (logical) content, the other is emotional and artistic. That is why the perception and understanding of the work is a complex, and often contradictory process, during which many people learn students achieve only the first level of assimilation of the content of the work.

The understanding of a literary text moves from the verbal to the objective, the combination of which gives a logical understanding; from it, the movement is directed to the understanding of motives, goals, and subtext.

In this direction, approximately, the process of perception of the actual and emotional-artistic content of the work takes place.

The understanding of the first level of the work (its actual content) occurs mainly through the explanation (clarification) of its verbal and conceptual material. There is a logical activity that requires lengthy comments, primarily to clarify the meaning of words, the meaning of concepts, the realities of reality.

However, when studying fiction, it is necessary to raise the student to the second level of perception (understanding) of the work, to the level of understanding its emotional and artistic content. Here the teacher tries to use such techniques of working with an artistic text that deepen his emotional perception, enrich such perception when the student penetrates into the artistic fabric of the work.

The process of understanding is not only complicated, but also contradictory. There may be a contradiction between the perception of the actual (logical) and emotional-artistic content of the work. The first stage of perception, as we know, leads to an understanding of the logical (actual) content of the work. To stop only here means to enter into a contradictory attitude to the subsequent work on a literary text, moreover, to slow it down. The achievement of logical understanding is not addressed to the emotional activity of students, does not rely on the awakening and development of their recreating imagination, what we call the culture of reading works of art of the word. However, it is impossible to pass the first stage of perception in any way, it underlies the achievement of the main goal of studying fiction — its emotional and artistic perception.

This is where difficulties arise: "These are two difficulties: first, so that children understand an exemplary work and, second, so that children feel it - in practice, they often contradict one another. Lengthy detailed explanations of a poetic work weaken its impression on the feeling, and on the other hand, an impression on the feeling is possible only when the exemplary work is completely understandable."

The contradiction of the two goals of understanding (two stages) takes on another form in school practice — the contradiction between the tasks of analyzing a work of art. Often the analysis is reduced only to the expansion of students' knowledge (the character of the character, the ideological meaning of the work, its historical and literary significance, etc.). In other words, the analysis represents only abstract-logical activity and does not affect the emotional side of the student's personality in any way. Meanwhile, a genuine analysis of the work, causing the intellectual activity of students, should simultaneously deepen their emotional perception of the literary text, enrich their emotional world.

There is only one way out here — the right combination of activities in the educational process to reveal the verbal-conceptual (logical) and emotional-artistic content of the work, constant attention to the enrichment of students' knowledge and the emotional wealth of their personality.

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